

DEVELOPMENT OF SINGLE CRYSTALLINE SILICON SOLAR CELLS LAY-DOWN PROCESS ON COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Recently, photovoltaic power energy appears to be one of the major technologies for the global sheared concerns in protecting environment. Up until now, many studies for the development of solar cell have focused on better stability and higher efficiency. However, the solar industry will be developed for combining solar cells to various kinds of structures. Light-weight composite is suitable for the structures which need high specific strength and stiffness. Nowadays the solar cell bonding to skins of buildings, vehicles, or electrical devices is a big issue [1]. The research paper on bonding thin-film silicon solar cell to CFRP composite was published in reference [2]. However, there are many possibilities for the solar cell bonding process depending on the combination of materials.

In this study, the solar cell bonding method to composite plate was developed. Single crystalline silicon solar cell was used in this study. The electrical performance of solar cell was monitored after applying 0.3% strain and 0.75% strain load to the specimen.

2 Experiments

2.1 High efficiency photovoltaic module

The single crystalline silicon solar cell, which has the highest energy efficiency among various kinds of solar cells, was used in this study (Fig. 1). The cells were cut for making specimens by specific laser cutting machine to avoid any possible defect. Then we coated protection layer on the top side of solar cell with ethylene tetrafluoroethylene (ETFE) and used bonding material ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) in general usage (Fig. 2, table 1) [2,3].

2.2 Bonding methods

Adhesive materials and bonding methods are very important. There are various kinds of factors which affect the structural stability for adhesively bonded solar cells to composite plates. Particularly, the adhesive material for aircrafts should be selected to guarantee high reliability of adhesion during the flight. The secondary bonding method with three types of adhesion materials (EVA film, Resin film, Elastic adhesive) were studied in this study.

2.3 Test specimen preparation

The specimen were made of carbon fiber unidirectional prepreg and woven type of glass/epoxy. The carbon prepreg sheets were cut to 250 x 250 mm size and then six plies of [45/0/-45]_s symmetric laminate were stacked and glass-epoxy sheets were placed on both sides. The standard curing process was applied [4]. Fig.3 and Fig.4 illustrate the test specimens with solar cell and the experimental setup for tensile test [1].

Fig. 1. Schematic of solar module; (top) cross-section, (bottom) front and rear sides.

Fig. 2. Performance characterization of as-received single crystalline silicon solar module.

	$V_{oc}(V)$	$J_{sc}(mA/cm^2)$	Fill factor	Efficiency(%)
Avg.	0.65	44.01	0.6241	17.49

Table 1 The average performance of as-received single crystalline silicon solar modules.

Fig. 3. Description of test specimen.

Fig. 4. Experimental setup for tensile test .

3 Test results

3.1 Electrical properties

Fig. 5 shows the solar modules J - V characteristics of each specimen after tensile test [3]. When EVA and Resin film were used as bonding materials, their electrical performance were gradually decreased after test, whereas elastic adhesive bonding case has no significant decreasing trend after test.

Fig. 5. Performance characteristics of a solar modules after tensile test; (top) EVA film; (middle) Resin film; (bottom) Elastic adhesive.

3.2 Adhesive thickness control

Figure 5 shows that the elastic adhesive is suitable for bonding material. Figure 6 shows the effect of adhesive thickness on electrical performance after applying load.

Fig. 6. Performance characteristics of solar modules various adhesive thickness at 0.75% strain (120 μ m, 240 μ m, 360 μ m, 460 μ m, 570 μ m).

4 Summaries

The single crystalline silicon solar module lay-down process was developed on the CFRP using the secondary-bonding method. Elastic adhesive material was suitable for maintaining good electrical performance regardless of loading or adhesion thickness. The basic principles for bonding brittle silicon cell to the various kinds of structural surface can be predicted. Further study will be performed under various temperature conditions.

References

- [1] J. C. Kim, Y. S. Lee, J. H. Lee, I. K. Choi, D. H. Kim, S. K. Cheong "A study on the solar cell lay-down for solar powered aircraft using secondary-bonding method". *KSME*, pp 399-403, 2010.
- [2] K. J. Maung, H. T. Hahn, Y.S. Ju "Multifunctional integration of thin-film silicon solar cells on carbon-fiber-reinforced epoxy composites". *Solar Energy*, Vol. 84, pp 450-458, 2010.
- [3] A. G. Aberle "Fabrication and characterisation of crystalline silicon thin-film materials for solar cells". *Thin Solid Films*, Vol. 511-512, pp 26-34, 2006.
- [4] S. H. Lee, H. Noguchi, S. K. Cheong "Tensile properties and fatigue characteristics of hybrid composites with non-woven carbon tissue". *International Journal of Fatigue*, Vol. 24, pp 397-405, 2008.
- [5] J. A. Foster, G. S. Aglietti "The thermal environment encountered in space by a multifunctional solar array". *Aerospace Science and Technology*, Vol. 12, pp 213-219, 2010.